

CONTENT OF FORMING LIFE SKILLS IN STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15709375>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 16th June 2025

Accepted: 20th June 2025

Online: 21st June 2025

KEYWORDS

Life skills, education,
students, personal
development,
communication, critical
thinking, emotional
intelligence, problem-
solving, decision-making,
curriculum integration,
21st-century skills.

ABSTRACT

This article explores the essential content and components involved in forming life skills among students. It emphasizes the importance of equipping learners with practical, emotional, and cognitive skills necessary for everyday challenges and future success. Key aspects such as communication, problem-solving, decision-making, emotional intelligence, critical thinking, and self-management are discussed in detail. The article also highlights the role of educational institutions and educators in integrating life skills into the curriculum through active, student-centered teaching strategies. The findings support the idea that systematic life skills education enhances students' personal development, academic performance, and social adaptability.

Today's society requires a person to act actively, make independent decisions, adapt to changing conditions, find their place in life, and achieve success in their profession, as well as the coherence of the reforms being implemented in the education system and the harmony of the requirements of the times.

In our educational programs implemented in the education system, the goal is not only to study knowledge theoretically, but also to educate a mature person who can apply the knowledge he has learned in life, appropriately use the information that quickly enters our lives, and carry out creative work.

In order to update language education, one of the main tasks was to develop a curriculum that provides for the combination of mandatory and variable components, with the development of independent creative abilities of students as a priority, and a draft National Curriculum for the Mother Tongue was developed and submitted to the public.

The main tasks of the methodology of the national curriculum for general secondary education are "independent work on one's "I", intellectual potential, spirituality and worldview, and the formation of 21st century skills (such as civilized communication, human virtue, reading literacy, critical and creative thinking, creativity, teamwork, problem-solving) in students".

Based on the demands of today, it is important to educate active citizens for life and closely assist them in achieving high goals. These four important ideas, which are defined as essential skills, are: leadership and entrepreneurship, media literacy, prevention and

combating violence, and the development of global citizenship skills. Creativity is at the heart of these skills.

In the process of developing life skills, it is important to adhere to the following general pedagogical and didactic principles: the principle of goal-orientedness, the principle of developmental education, the principles of scientificity, gradualism, continuity, the principle of unity of education and upbringing, the principles of moving from familiar to unfamiliar, from easy to difficult, from simple to complex, the principle of taking into account errors made by students in their oral and written speech, the principle of relying on their level of knowledge, and the principle of practical orientation.

Below, we will focus on the speech topics and texts within which life skills are taught in the process of mother tongue education by grade.

Content of education on media and information literacy

These aspects are given special attention in the National Curriculum within the following topics:

Grade VIII

Who is a journalist? (Journalist, reporter, editor)

Exercises related to identifying grammatical and stylistic errors in information texts provided on social networks, and editing them.

Editor of the school newspaper

Language units related to the press, their pronunciation and spelling. Exercises and tasks related to determining the meanings of terms related to the field, using them in oral and written speech.

Grade X

Conducting a group discussion on the topic "The role of written sources in the fate of humanity" and creating a discussion text on this basis.

Creating a creative text based on one of the topics: "Letter to a friend", "Hello, dear diary!", "If I were a blogger".

Preparing a presentation on the topic "This is what suits me", comparing articles from newspapers and online publications. The use of linguistic units in literary and informational texts.

What is said in this? What can the title of the text show about the text. Determining the main idea of the text. Determining the units that reveal the theme and idea of the text. Getting acquainted with the text "What is SEO (QTO)?", completing exercises and tasks. Arguing on the topic of the disproportion of songs and clips.

The role of gestures in speech expression. Expression of emotions. Expression of attitudes. "Images" (stickers) that express reactions in social networks. Replacing them with words. To create an understanding of the role of gestures in speech expression through an excerpt from the story "Horror". Prove ideas with real-life examples, discuss "images" that express reactions in social networks.

Words specific to dialect. Phrases.

For the exercise "Let's talk in literary language!", form a list of five programs broadcast on TV channels whose hosts speak in dialect. Expression of attitudes. To draw conclusions

about the richness of the dialect of the Uzbek language, but also about the need to keep the literary language pure.

Grade XI

Where and by whom was this said?

Work on a text entitled "Can I believe this?" that provides information about the social network and methods for checking the accuracy of various information circulating among the people.

Preparing a presentation on the topic "How would I describe it?"

Speaking of graphic images... Graphic information. The order of presenting information in a graphic form. Methods of presenting information in a graphic form (diagram, table, graphic organizer). Listening to an audio text on the topic "Red, yellow, green zones" and describing it in a graphic form.

Why is this needed?

Advertising texts, the use of language units in them. Types of advertising. Working on the text "Marketing and advertising". Finding out what it is about from silent advertising images. Preparing an advertising presentation for a product whose instructions are written.

The content of education on the development of global citizenship skills

The national curriculum stipulates that the formation of socio-emotional and civic competencies consists of acquiring knowledge about civic duty, social and political development, emergencies, environmental problems, and understanding artistic and artistic works, as well as developing organizational skills in their preservation.

Grade VIII

Speech topic "Find a solution to the problem". Reading the discussion text on the topic "I want to change the world", responding to the content of the text, continuing the topic. Being able to sort out thoughts for a written text from an orally composed text, ensuring its consistency, writing short notes, making a plan and preparing an essay draft.

The Awakening of the West

Creating a text on the topic "What is value for me?" and expressing an oral opinion on this topic. Expressing an opinion on the general picture of today's world in written and oral form. To engage in a group discussion about which values require to keep up with today's world.

Create a text on the topic "I bet on the future, not on a grand wedding."

Administrative responsibility

Exercises and tasks related to the review of codes, analysis of language units used in them, grammatical forms, and assessment of the style of expression. To express laws and articles in writing in a way that is understandable to the public, while being able to select the necessary language units, and explain legal terms.

Grade IX

I serve my homeland (army, patriotism, defense of the country)

Organize a debate on the topic "How is the homeland protected?". Write a letter to a soldier.

"Strength is in justice" (justice, law, trust - the basic concepts of society)

Get acquainted with information on legislation and compliance with it from reliable official sites, prepare a presentation reflecting your attitude to this information text and present it.

Tourism is the basis of our economy (tourism in Uzbekistan, ways to develop it)

Create a descriptive text about a historical city or exhibit based on a given picture.

The role of sciences in human life (science and society, science and everyday life)

Engage in a group on the topic "Will the world improve in the future or..." Express conclusions orally and in writing.

Create an analytical text on the topic "The future of humanity in my imagination".

World Wars (economic, political, social consequences of world wars)

Reading the text "Temur's Advice", discussing the role of order, discipline and responsibility in human life.

What did the West learn from the East? (crusades, influence of Muslim culture on the West)

When will I vote too? (elections, right to vote)

Getting acquainted with the ballot, analyzing the style of expression of official business papers, language units used in them, grammatical forms.

Foreign policy (foreign policy of Uzbekistan, ambassadors).

Collecting and presenting material on the political situation in the international arena, expressing one's thoughts without deviating from the topic.

Grade X

Concepts of the universe and ecology.

Creating an analytical text on the topic "My life and global ecological problems". Entering into a group discussion on the topic of the impact of the environment on human health.

Grade XI

"The life of every nation, which shows its existence in the world, is language and literature... . The harmony of language and literature. Working with the text of Nodir Jonuzak's poem "My Heart's Language".

Legal terms. Distinctive features of legal terms. Conversation about the legal status of a person in his relationship with the state.

Preparation and oral presentation exercises on the topic "Do you know your rights?"

Educational content on the development of leadership skills

Grade VIII

Ozone layer (depletion of the ozone layer, ecology)

Collecting evidence and information for a scientific essay on the topic of nature protection, sorting them, making a plan and presenting them in a coherent manner.

What is DNA? (DNA, genetics)

Creating a scientific text related to the topic based on the "Little Researcher" exercise. Exercises on achieving scientific substantiation of ideas and appropriate use of terms.

Marketer (trade, marketing, modern professions)

Collecting information on the selection of names of retail stores, consumer service outlets, organizations, enterprises and institutions, their spelling, and preparing a critical journalistic text on this information.

Online stores (amazon, alibaba, olx)

Drawing up a simple and complex plan for an essay on the topic “Everything is on the Internet”. When drawing up a plan, pay attention to the consistency of content, be able to express the relevance of the topic.

Preparing an advertising text for a product of your choice. Exercises and tasks related to the use of advertising language units, following the rules for preparing advertisements, and preparing a logo for your product.

Freedom of speech

Exercises and tasks related to assessing the reliability, accuracy, and correctness of the information provided, as well as the forms of its publication.

To be able to apply the knowledge gained in the essay on a free topic based on the exercise “I am wrong, but my opinion is mine” in practice.

In the curriculum, life skills are formed on the basis of the principle of integrativeness within the framework of the following speech topics: “Me, you, he and they”; “Blessings of nature”; “Healthy body - healthy mind”; “My profession - my pride”; “Young economist”; “Science and technologies”; “Language and heart”; “Treasures of history”; “Art and culture”; “Our rights - our rights”.

In conclusion, it can be said that in native language education, life skills such as global citizenship, media and information literacy, leadership, and combating violence and a culture of peace are developed through pictures, texts, practical projects, and presentations selected for the speech topics given within the curriculum.

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